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ABSTRACT

Deliverable 1.2 carried out a literature review highlighting the drivers and constraints on the utilization of key waste streams on agricultural soils. In this report, we particularly focused on animal manure, food waste, sewage sludge and crop residues, combined with key processing/conversion techniques, i.e. composting, anaerobic digestion and biochar. Many of these waste streams (not all) will be assessed at different (decision making and geographic) levels in BioCASH, considering not only the agronomic indicators but also macro-economic aspects regarding their availability in Europe. This report is a continuation of the work carried out by SLU in deliverable 1.1., of which the focus was a literature review derived from European-based projects. Deliverable 1.2 (originated from tasks 1.2) provide important knowledge to the BioCASH project on the potential use of different waste streams and will be surely put into perspective as the results on the experiments that are produced in WP3.

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1. Introduction

In BioCASH proposal, task 1.2 was aimed at identifying promising waste streams supply chains that could be potentially assessed on the experimental and analytical WP3 of BioCASH. The identification would be mainly sourced from a scientific and grey literature review, interviews with stakeholders and internal agreements within the consortium. However, given our modeling and lab experiment limitations, the consortium agreed that all identified waste streams are not able to be entirely assessed (i.e. at both physical-lab level with soil and product samples, and regional level with the BioCASH modeling toolbox) in the course of the project. The (technical) reasons will be presented in the final reports and also mentioned in the EJP monitoring reports during the execution of WP3 and WP4. Therefore, we

In this report, a full review on promising waste streams supply chains is carried out not only on the resource perspective but also on the processing techniques. In addition, we presented the impacts of these waste streams on several soil health indicators and the most suitable soil types for each waste stream assessed. We also describe existing farming systems that could utilize these waste streams. Lastly, we conducted an interview with several stakeholders in Lithuania, of which we discussed the willingness to adopt renewable fertilizers from waste streams on agricultural soils.

Task 1.2 should be seen as an extension of the work carried out in task 1.1 with a more in-depth description of waste streams supply chains. This large overview will be put into perspective in the forthcoming project reports of BioCASH as we present the results of the experimental and analytical WP3 are produced.

2. Sources of organic waste.

Organic waste represents a substantial share of European municipal waste generation. Every year 2.2 billion tons of waste are generated in the EU. Between 2010 and 2019, the EU has produced a slightly higher amount of agricultural wastes, co-products, and byproducts than all other countries, with an estimated 18.4 billion tons, or 2.6 billion tons per year (Bedoić et al., 2019). Due to the considerable volume, the EU's common objectives for waste management cannot be met without addressing the bio-waste stream. Organic waste streams are an essential area of research due to the increasing amount of waste produced globally and the inherent potential to be converted into valuable products. Organic wastes are generated from different sources/activities ranging from households and urban activities (e.g., food waste biowastes, sewage sludges, and green wastes), agriculture (manures and crop residues), and non-agriculture (e.g. food waste from households and industry).

2.1. Food waste

Food waste is an essential component of the municipal bio-waste stream, with a high potential for contributing to a more circular economy. Around 88 million tons of food waste are generated annually in the EU. It can be divided into avoidable and non-avoidable food waste. Food waste (i.e. household kitchen waste) is an integral part of the biodegradable bio-waste stream, different than

park and garden waste (green waste). In terms of bio-waste composition, the former comprises the largest share, but most are lost to landfills and incinerators. (Manfredi et al., 2015).

In contrast, green waste is the only fraction collected for recycling in many EU countries. Ideally, food waste can be generated across the entire food supply chain (from production to consumption), with the largest share generated at consumption. On a per capita basis, much more food is wasted by households in industrialized/wealthier countries than in developing ones. Food losses occur significantly at the downstream stages of the supply chain in countries with medium and high incomes. In contrast, food loss occurs in low-income countries at the early stages of the supply chain due to limited harvesting techniques, inadequate storing and cooling facilities, unfavorable climatic conditions, poor infrastructure, and insufficient processing, packaging, and marketing systems (Bräutigam et al., 2014).

Food waste poses environmental, ethical, and economic questions and highlights the malfunctioning of our food system.

Major contributors to food waste are highlighted below:

Households (48%)

- Bad/Inadequate storage
- Discarding leftovers, Discarding parts
- Wastage
- Excessive buying, overconsumption/proportion

Wholesale & Retails (7%)

- Packaging defects
- Overstocking
- Temperature changes (Storage)
- Standards/Expiration

Food processing and manufacturing (25%)

- Damaged products
- Overproduction
- Byproducts/residual products
- Discarded products.

Restaurants and food services (9%)

- Customers preferences
- Customers demand
- Leftovers/indecision by customers

Primary Production (11%)

2.2. Animal Manure

Livestock farming constitutes about 50% of agricultural Production in Europe. Livestock farming systems vary from country to country and sometimes from region to region due to the range of landscape, climate, and cultures within Europe. A critical product generated from livestock farming is manure. Manure (also known as livestock manure) is organic matter, primarily derived from animal

faeces and urine, but typically also containing plant material (often straw), which has been used as animal bedding and has absorbed the feces and urine. Animals are raised under different production systems, influencing specific manure management systems and strategies. Manure produced by animals in range and pasturelands is usually managed using techniques different from those employed for confined animals. With approximately 120 million tons of manure per year from cattle, pig, and poultry livestock, not including those on pasture, the animal manure management system is an integral part of the agricultural waste management system.

The major sources of manures are:

- Cattle shed waste dung, urine, and slurry from biogas plants.
- Farmyard manure- decomposed mixture of dung and urine of farm animals along with litter and leftover material from roughages or fodder fed to the cattle.
- Poultry litter, droppings of sheep, pig, cattle and goat
- Slaughterhouse wastes-bone meal, meat meal, blood meal, horn and hoof meal, Fish wastes

2.3. Sewage sludge

Sewage sludge (SS) is the byproduct generated from wastewater treatment plants. The sludge contains organic matter, nutrients, and heavy metals, making it suitable for land application. However, pathogens and contaminants in the sludge can be detrimental to human health and the environment. Therefore, proper treatment and management of sewage sludge are essential.

SS is primarily generated as end products from municipal and industrial wastewater facilities' mechanical, biological, and physicochemical treatment. In the EU, the biological treatment of wastewater is one of the largest industries, producing millions of tons of SS annually. Most industrial wastewater and municipal waste rich in organic load are mostly treated by biological treatment, although with some limitations of poorly degraded chemical compounds such as pesticides and antibiotics. The storage of sewage sludge can be challenging, especially when stored directly on the soil surface due to its fermentation capacity and the presence of unsafe and persistent substances such as pathogens, heavy metals, and other inorganic substances (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons). Additionally, the storage of sewage sludge in landfills influences leaching production and CO₂ emission directly into the air.

3. Treatment processes of organic wastes

Available data shows that the amount of waste and its management differs significantly across EU countries (see also BioCASH deliverable 1.1), with all agreeing to more recycling. Recycling organic waste is therefore crucial for meeting the EU target to recycle 65 % of municipal waste by 2035. This includes both organic waste that is separately collected and the ones collected together with mixed (residual) waste but excludes home-composted bio-waste.

To reduce waste and its impact on the environment, the EU has adopted ambitious targets for recycling and landfill and is working on an efficient circular economy. The EU wants to promote the

prevention of waste and the reuse of products as much as possible. When this is not possible, recycling (including composting) is preferred, followed by using waste to generate energy. The most harmful option for the environment and people's health is simply disposing of waste in a landfill, although it is also one of the cheapest possibilities. Even though the waste generated per capita has increased, how we manage waste has improved - with more recycling and composting and a decrease in landfill.

Composting and anaerobic digestion have remained the mainstream of biowastes treatments/recycling in Europe, with about 35-40% of biowaste processed through these treatments. However, still more than 50 % of bio-waste waste in Europe is incinerated or landfilled.

3.1. Anaerobic digestion (AD)

Anaerobic digestion of organic waste: Among the waste treatment technologies, anaerobic digestion can be considered the best available technique for treating organic fraction of organic waste treatment technologies. Additionally, AD is the most used method for converting organic waste into biogas, which can be used for heating and energy generation. This technology offers benefits for the environment, energy, and economy. Anaerobic digestion has effectively treated different types of organic waste, including municipal solid waste, food waste, sewage sludge, and agricultural waste. In this process, microorganisms break down the organic matter in the absence of oxygen, producing biogas, a mixture of methane and carbon dioxide.

3.2. Composting

Composting is another sustainable method for treating and converting organic waste into organic amendments/useful products that can be utilized in the agricultural system. This technique involves the breakdown of organic matter via microorganisms in the presence of oxygen, producing a nutrient-rich soil amendment. Composting can be used to treat a variety of organic waste streams, including food waste, yard waste, and agricultural waste. Composting is generally defined as the controlled biological decomposition of organic material under predominantly aerobic conditions that allow the development of "thermophilic" temperatures through biologically produced heat. The composting process produces a final product that is sanitized, stabilized, high in humic substances and can be applied to land. Applying compost to land is beneficial as it adds valuable organic matter, improving soil structure, and adding valuable macro- and micro-nutrients and microorganisms back to the soil to improve its health.

3.3. Pyrolysis

A thermochemical process in which biomass is subjected to high thermal decomposition in the absence of oxygen, producing solid, liquid and gaseous products (Lohri et al., 2017). Pyrolysis allows the transformation of low-energy-density materials into high-energy-density biofuels and the recovery of higher-value products. One of its advantages is that many types of raw material can be used, including industrial and domestic residues, but making pyrolysis economically viable remains challenging.

3.3.1. Biochar production from pyrolysis

Biochar is a form of charcoal that is produced by heating biomass material in the absence of oxygen. Biochar can be used as a soil amendment, as it can improve soil fertility and water retention. Several studies have focused on the Production of biochar from different types of organic waste, including forestry residues, agricultural waste, and municipal solid waste.

4. Waste streams supply chains in Europe and their impact on soil health

In Europe, there is a growing awareness of the potential environmental and economic advantages of combining various organic waste streams in a circular approach in relation to how they are processed. Literature reviews on soil health indicators were made to demonstrate the influence of these organic waste streams and their corresponding processed products on to measure and assess changes in soil properties and functioning to understand soil health. The soil health indicators were categorized according to specific physical, chemical, and biological indicators to verify soil status use.

Table 1. Impact on soil health indicators of food waste streams.

	Food Waste Compost	Food Waste Biochar	Food Waste Digestate
pH, EC, Soil Chemical characteristics	Compost will improve soil C and N more than fertilizer. Food waste compost enhanced moisture content. Soil pH not influenced by food waste compost over short- and long-term application.	Soil pH is enhanced under biochar addition is related to the higher pH of the biochar itself and its liming effect. Higher pH and EC might be due to the higher porosity and surface area of biochar which together with applied fertilizers might have improved the soil physicochemical properties through nutrient retention on biochar surfaces resulting in higher pH and EC.	1) Lignin content in FWD higher compared to food waste, due to the low biodegradability of the complex organic polymer in the AD process. 2) High nutrient Concentration, high water retention capacity.
Crop biometric parameters	Food compost can stimulate plant growth and replace synthetic fertilizers, but the effects vary by plant species and waste feed to composters.	FWD biochars were unable to cast any additional benefit on crop's physiological parameters such as chlorophyll index.	Increase in all indices of crop growth: stem length, root development, leaf index, nutrient uptake.
Crop yield	Increase of soil fertility and yields, from the application of compost over short- and long-term application.	1) Integrated use of food waste biochar with mineral fertilizer	FWD provided even better fertilizer performance through improving crop yield and

		<p>increased crop production.</p> <p>2) The reduced or lower crop growth performance under sole application of biochar (FWB) might be due to the clogging of micropores and reduced availability of crop nutrients.</p>	<p>chlorophyll content in plants.</p>
<p>Metalloids and contaminants</p>	<p>1) Presence of trace heavy metal in food waste compost. The presence of Cr and Ni were probably due to compost production stage such as mixing or grinding stage and from sources of food waste. Cr is highly used in metallic uses. In stainless steel, average Cr content is about 17 % mostly from kitchenware and other small items. Hence, it may have higher chances during the composting stage, peels, dust and plastics ware coats from working utensils may end up in the mixture of compost.</p>	<p>Food waste Biochar amendment does not eradicate but stabilizes heavy metals in soil, transforming the toxic elements into less soluble and less bio-accessible forms.</p>	<p>FWB represents a potential biofertilizer considering its low contents of metals/metalloids and pathogenic microorganisms.</p>
<p>Microbial composition and benefits</p>	<p>Food waste compost comprised of high carbohydrate content, and it was easily used as carbon and energy source by microorganism. Food waste compost contained not only a high carbon content but also a high nitrogen content. The carbon and nitrogen in food waste compost could be easily used as energy and nutrient source for soil microorganisms, and this resulted in increased soil microbial populations and soil biomass.</p>	<p>Food waste biochar enhanced soil microbial composition. Soil enzymatic activities improved when not over applied with biochar.</p>	<p>The solid digestate might contain beneficial microorganisms which can inhibit harmful fungal pathogens, suggesting the potential of digestate in improving soil fertility and nurturing beneficial microbial community.</p>
<p>GHG emissions</p>	<p>The use of compost in agriculture has a positive effect in GHG emissions since its</p>	<p>Emissions were not significantly influenced especially as it relates to</p>	<p>FWB contains a higher amount of partially</p>

	<p>application as an organic amendment provokes that carbon stays bound to soil, although the content of other nutrients (N, P, etc.) is typically low. GHG emissions from composting processes depend on the waste type and composition.</p> <p>GHG emissions from composting processes are highly dependent on the waste type and composition</p>	<p>methane and nitrous oxide.</p>	<p>degraded organic matter and NH₄</p> <p>+N content compared to digestate derived from other feeds such as agricultural residue and animal manure. The high organic matter content in FWD might improve soil physical properties, and the slightly alkaline nature of FWD could be beneficial for contaminant immobilization in degraded farmland. However, the application of FWD might increase NH₃ emission</p>
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Table 2. Impact on soil health indicators of sewage sludge waste streams.

	Sewage sludge compost	Sewage sludge Biochar	Sewage sludge digestate
Constituents parameters such as yield	<p>SSC is useful for enhancing crop production, as well as the accumulation of nutrients and organic matter in the soil. Affects the germination and development of seedlings.</p> <p>The SS application alone did not provide the plants with mineral nutrients in appropriate values, while the combination of SS preparation with nitrogen-containing fertilizers significantly improved the plant growth and promoted plant development.</p>	<p>The SSB yield percentage significantly decreases with the increasing pyrolysis temperature. These changes are caused by the gradual decomposition of organic substances in SS at various temperatures.</p>	<p>Sewage sludge usually contains high organic matter and macro and micronutrients, its application in soil improves soil properties and consequently increases plant productivity.</p>
Heavy metals presence	<p>In the longer term, significant Cu and Zn accumulation are expected to occur in the soil affected by repeated applications of</p>	<p>1) Various SS contains metal (loid)s with a higher boiling point than the pyrolysis temperature employed, which gets finally concentrated in biochar. The pyrolysis also enhances the thermo-stability of metal (loid)s,</p>	<p>The application of sewage sludge may lead to the accumulation of heavy metals in soil and crops, which can result in phytotoxic effects</p>

	<p>sewage sludge composts displaying similarly high Cu and Zn concentrations. However, in short term application, no statistically significant metal enrichment can be noticed in the compost-amended soil.</p>	<p>however various metal (loid)s was present in SS such as mineral salts, hydroxides, sulfides and other were converted to sulphides or oxides with better thermo-stability during reductive pyrolytic condition. Thus, the metal (loid)s remained in biochar.</p> <p>2) It is advisable to use pyrolysis temperatures which are higher than 600 °C in order to obtain low toxicity levels, to be suitable for agricultural applications.</p>	<p>and accumulation of heavy metals in food supplies.</p>
Soil chemical parameters	<p>Positively increases the contents of soil organic carbon, total nitrogen, available nitrogen, and total phosphorus required by plant. Comparison of physicochemical characteristics of SS of different origins showed that average concentrations of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium.</p>	<p>Long-term benefits regarding nutrient availability include organic matter stabilization, slow nutrient release and enhanced retention of cations due to the increase in cation exchange capacity.</p> <p>SB affects soil properties, e.g., increasing pH, C, N, P, K, and water retention, thus changing the conditions for microbial activity.</p>	<p>Sewage sludge digestate application increased plant biomass and yield.</p>
GHG emissions	<p>Very limited literature.</p>	<p>Sewage sludge biochar may help to offset GHGs. The impact of biochar on GHG emissions may be influenced by its properties (e.g., pyrolysis temperature, feedstock, dose), as well as the land use and soil moisture level</p>	<p>Sewage sludge digestate exert a positive impact on the environment by reducing greenhouse gas emissions</p>

Table 3. Impact on soil health indicators of manure based waste streams.

	Manure compost	Manure Biochar	Manure digestate
Soil chemical parameters	<p>Soil P and K increased linearly with increased compost rates. Additionally, soil organic matter increased with compost rates. A common concern with application of manure compost is that its soluble salts can accumulate in the soil and become detrimental to crop growth. The current trend, however, is to</p>	<p>Manure biochar contain nutrients such as mg, Ca that are very valuable to crops in poor soils that are limited in these nutrients.</p> <p>Biochar as a substance is mainly recommended for acidic soils as it alkalizes the pH and improves nutrient retention through cation adsorption.</p>	<p>Increased major chemical nutrients over long term application Depending on the dose, the digestate could contain compounds inhibitory to ammonia-oxidizing activity.</p>

	use low-salt rations for finishing cattle, which lowers the salt content of the manure.		
Soil physical parameters	Manure compost play an important role in maintaining soil fertility. Increased EC in manure compost amended soil but still within acceptable EC threshold.	Manure biochar improve the water holding capacity of soil, which could enhance crop yield conserving the rainfall water in arid regions	Enhances soil moisture and soil aggregate stability.

Crop residue incorporation in soils holds an important niche in sustainable agricultural practices. Crop residues provide organic C and N inputs to soils for maintaining or improving the soil stocks of these elements and, ultimately, soil health and crop productivity.

Table 4. Impact on soil health indicators of crop residues.

GHG Emission	Diverse residue types reportedly affect the magnitude of soil N ₂ O emission, and the high rate of soil N ₂ O emission is affected by the C/N ratio of the applied residue. (Janz et al., 2021). Complete retention of crop residues also resulted in an increase of soil N ₂ O emissions by 17–30% on the longer term (Haas et al., 2022)
Carbon stocks & nutrient cycling	Conflicting results as regards the quantification of residue incorporation effect on soil organic carbon stocks. Some studies reported a maintenance or further improvement of soil C stocks (Haas et al., 2022; Janz et al., 2021). Crop residue incorporation increases the SOC concentrations. (Poeplau et al., 2015) reported SOC losses, SOC stabilization or even non-significant or negligible impact in long term studies.
Crop production & yield	Positive results on crop yield with significant effect when other organic materials (poultry manure) were added to crop residues acting as an additional N source. The efficiency highly dependent on crop characteristics (Piccoli et al., 2020). (Hiel et al., 2018) reported the effect of crop residue management was not noticeable in short period rather in longer time frame, highly dependent on the local pedo-climatic conditions and a multiple of other interacting components of the agro-ecosystem. The effects of crop residue on crop yields are contradictory based on different literature reviews/studies. Some studies reported the presence of residues to be detrimental to crop germination/emergence as they can form a physical obstacle for seedlings (Arvidsson et al., 2014) can create a cold and humid micro-climate around the seed and provide a favourable habitat for slugs and plant pathogens (Lemtiri* et al., 2016). Some other indirect effects include residue mineralization, which leads to more nutrients available for the plants or the presence of organic matter from residues modifying the soil structure and therefore modifying the root system development.
Soil health parameters	Crop residue retention in agricultural systems generally increases soil porosity (especially the large pores) and reduces soil bulk density, regardless of tillage practice, soil's physical properties, namely soil bulk density,

	<p>porosity, soil penetration resistance, soil moisture, and other soil and crop parameters (Fu et al., 2021; Mirzaei et al., 2021; Sarker et al., 2022).</p> <p>The removal/non incorporation of crop residues also decreases the soil water holding capacity, soil structural stability, soil water <u>infiltration</u> as well as increase soil bulk density and erosion. These are factors that may influence negatively crop productivity and ecosystem services. Crop residues sustain decomposer food webs in arable soil; therefore, removing crop residues denies a source of energy for soil biological activity and growth with potentially negative impacts on nutrient retention and <u>soil biodiversity</u> (Abalos et al., 2022).</p>
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5. Soil types

Soil varies enormously in characteristics, capacity, and nutritional composition. Each soil types distinct strengths and weaknesses ensure that waste streams meet differing soil needs for optimal performance in agricultural production. There is a need for a deeper understanding of the influence of waste stream application on the quality of different soil types since not every soil has the same advantage of a waste stream/product application. Soil is used to provide and meet many ecosystem services. They can be generally categorized into sandy, silty, clay, loam, and peat soil based on the dominating size of the particles within the soil.

Table 5. Suitability of waste streams on different soil types.

Food waste compost (FWC)	Food waste biochar	Food waste digestate
<p>The nutritional composition of FWC makes it readily suitable for sandy soil. It contributes to improving n the soil attributes necessary for plant growth. All soil types are suitable for use with FWC.</p>	<p>All soil types are suitable for use with FWC. An important part of this discussion is the ability of biochar to increase soil porosity, water holding capacity and soil structure, making the soil less dense with better soil aeration. Hence it is suitable for application in clay, sandy and silt soil (Mustafa et al., 2022; Rasa et al., 2018)</p>	<p>Applicable in all soil types (loam, clay, sandy, sandy loam) due to its rich nutrient contents and abundant organic matter (Mustafa et al., 2022)</p>
Sewage sludge compost	Sewage sludge biochar	Sewage Sludge digestate
<p>The different soil types are suitable for sewage sludge compost with the aim of meeting/targeting specific soil components and crop needs. Sewage sludge compost could be planned for soils in different pedoclimatic zones (acidic sandy soils, loamy soils, silty loam soil. Of particular importance are soil with immediate restoration of soil fertility such as semiarid soils, where an immediate restoration</p>	<p>The specific characteristics of sewage sludge biochar (SSB) make it attractive and suitable for amendment in different soil types. SSB can be applied on loamy soil, sandy soil, acidic soil (to raise the pH), sandy loam soil and nutrient deficient soils.</p>	<p>Sewage sludge digestate is an effective biofertilizer in many soil types. Although SS application is Europe is regulated by various legislative acts guiding their management and doses, it is applied on soils such as claye silty, sandy clay soil, clay soil, loamy clay soil.</p>

of soil fertility is needed (Curci et al., 2020).		
Manure compost	Manure biochar	Manure digestate
Even though manure compost has an attribute of slow release of nutrients, it is suitable for a wide range of soil types due to its high organic matter content. It is suitable for application in sandy loam soil, sandy soil, silt loam, silty clay loam and clay soil. More extreme soils such as sandy and clay soils benefit more from manure compost.	With the availability of stable C in biochar, its benefits have been widely discussed in their application. Based on the fact that the type of feedstock influences the quality of biochar, manure biochar holds high quality compared to other types of biochar mainly due to its higher soil cation exchange capacity. It can be applied to different soil type such as loamy sand, sandy loam, or clay loam/sandy clay loam	There are no limits to the soil types on which manure digestates can be applied. Several studies have demonstrated/showed their application on wide range of soil (loam, clay, sandy, sandy loam with positive effects on soil health (biological, physical and chemical parameters).
Crop Residues		
Crop residues are an important source of organic matter. However, their impacts vary across soil types due to the specificity and characteristics of respective soil types. For instance, different soil textures affect residue breakdown and nutrient availability. Sandy soils with lower organic matter content and larger particles, stand to benefit more (water holding capacity and organic matter) from crop residue incorporation than loam and silt loam soils.		

6. Potential use of waste streams on different farming systems

Sustainable management and assessment of waste streams and processed waste in agriculture should be conducted on an individual basis, considering specific soil types, crop choices, farming systems, and environmental factors to maximize the benefits. In Europe, these waste streams and processed waste will play crucial roles in sustainable agriculture as they meet different needs across the agricultural landscape. The diversity and vitality of this class of waste streams ensure its utilization across different pedoclimatic zones with different soil types and farming systems. With 55% of Europe’s land surface being agricultural land, the major soil types under agricultural use subjected to these waste streams range from Cambisols, chromic Luvisols (northern Europe and the Mediterranean), Luvisols and dystric Gleysols (western and central Europe) and Chernozems and mollic Gleysols (southern part of eastern Europe) (Schad, 2016)

Digestates, green waste, food waste, and their respective processed waste can be used on a variety of soil, such as loamy, sandy, silt, and clay soils, but their suitability and application methods may vary. Individual waste streams play specific roles and functions when applied to soil.

To put this into perspective, the dynamism of farming systems has made it possible and necessary to utilize these waste streams to improve agricultural and environmental productivity. Moreover, the surge in intensive agriculture across Europe, which comes with its detriments, has necessitated improving nutrient management (recovery and use). The drive for farming systems to meet the

growing needs will involve applying one and/or a combination of different waste streams for agricultural and environmental sustainability. For instance, the Farm to Fork strategy of the European Commission (European Commission (EC), 2021) targeted a 25% increase in organic agriculture of total farmland by 2030, which the sustainable use of waste streams can achieve.

Organic agriculture/farming cautiously uses natural/bioresources to attain self-reliance and sustainability. The interconnectivity of organic agriculture and organic waste in Europe is firmly based on shared common principles of sustainability, resource conservation, and environmental protection. Hence, the waste streams hold huge potential to sufficiently bridge the gap in nutrient supply and circularity of bioresources with less reliance on chemical inputs/fertilizers (Reimer et al., 2023).

Conventional agriculture/farming is a widely used method worldwide to produce most of the food we eat. The conventional farming system involves large quantities of inputs, which, despite its known benefits to solving global needs, is considered unsustainable and thus has continued to generate environmental and ecological negative side-effects. This is poised to threaten its future use. Hence, efforts have been tailored towards incorporating organic waste streams, particularly organic waste, such as digestate, compost, and food waste, to complement and/or reduce reliance on synthetic fertilizers.

The discussion around **agroforestry** is generating much interest due to the synergies created by sustainable multifunctional systems that can provide a wide range of economic, sociocultural, and environmental benefits. Some studies have reemphasized that integrating agroforestry practices into organic farming systems can bring about a wholesome, sustained agroecological system inclined toward food security, ecological sustainability, and economic stability (Rosati et al., 2021; Selvan et al., 2023). The waste streams can be utilized in the agroforestry system to improve soil health, sequester carbon, improve soil biodiversity, and climate change mitigation (Augere-Granier, 2020).

Urban agriculture encourages a system-wide approach with the capacity to draw on waste streams to achieve multiple benefits across the agricultural and environmental systems. The utilization of waste streams in urban agriculture complements and amplifies the efficiency of food systems at different levels. These waste streams and their processed products are suitable for the various types of urban agriculture, such as street landscaping, green walls, vertical walls, and hydroponics/aquaponics, have been identified.

Integrated farming system

There are concerted efforts for efficient land use to achieve sustenance and sustainability where the byproduct of one component (waste streams) becomes the input for another component. Hence, integrated farming systems enhance the improvisation of agricultural methods, such as the application/amendments of these classes of waste streams to increase food production and enhance income from the farm.

7. Survey on the willingness of the farmers to adopt waste streams

The *EKOAgriTech* exhibition-forum on organic crop production technologies took place on 4 July 2023, Akademija, Lithuania. Four institutions have come together to organize the unique idea – Lithuanian Research Centre for agriculture and Forestry, the Lithuanian Organic Farms Association, The Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Services and Ekoagros company. Science, business, policy makers and the public talk a lot about sustainability, but not enough about what concrete actions should be taken to promote organic farming.

The participants of the *EKOAgriTech* exhibition took part in the survey of the European Horizon project "Bio-economy and circular agriculture for soil health" and provided their answers about the use of organic materials and their prospects to use it in agriculture. In total, 46 respondents participated in the survey, including 27 farmers, 4 entrepreneurs, 8 scientists, and 7 respondents chose the answer "other." The percentage distribution of survey participants is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Distribution of survey respondents.

2. Do you know what is circular economy?

- A) Yes
- B) No

Approximately, 25% of entrepreneurs and 35% of farmers answered that they do not know what circular economy is. Meanwhile, researchers and persons who identified themselves as "others" stated that they know 100% the definition of circular economy.

Figure 2. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 2

3. Do you agree that waste streams should be used in agricultural sector?

- A. Yes

B. No

Only 3.8% ,i.e. 1 farmer out of all respondents, did not agree on the use of waste streams in agriculture.

Figure 3. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 3

4. Do you apply it in your environment (farm, garden, horticulture)? For example, compost, use of manure as fertilizer

A) Yes

B) No

Among all the surveyed individuals, the people who identified themselves as entrepreneurs were the largest percentage of those who answered that they do not use organic materials in their activity (25% not using). It was surprising that even four farmers (14.8%) out of the respondents do not use soil organic materials in they practice.

Figure 4. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 4

5. What untreated waste streams have you ever used to improve soil quality and health?

A) Manure

B) Plant residues

C) Slurry

D) Sewage sludge

E) I don't use anything

More than 80% of the surveyed individuals have used manure as untreated soil improvement material, and over 65% have used plant residues to enhance soil quality and health. However, ~4% of the respondents have not used any untreated soil improvement materials.

Figure 5. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 5.

6. What treated waste streams have you ever used to improve soil quality and health?

- A) Compost
- B) Biochar
- C) Digestate
- D) I don't use anything

The most popular processed organic material used by respondents is compost, with a significant 67 percent stating that they use compost as a soil improvement substance. Biochar is a relatively new product, and there are no large factories in Lithuania producing a substantial amount of this product. As a result, none of the respondents have used biochar in they practice.

Figure 6. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 6.

7. Which waste streams haven't you used before but consider using to increase soil quality and health?

- A) Manure
- B) Plant residues
- C) Slurry
- D) Sewage sludge
- E) Compost
- F) Biochar
- G) Digestate
- H) I have not used it and I am not considering using it

Survey respondents' answers about the organic materials they haven't used before but would consider using in the future are distributed almost evenly. The most positive responses were

received for slurry, sewage sludge, and biochar (23.9%). Based on the provided answers, we can conclude that biochar is a promising product with future demand.

Figure 7. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 7.

8. In your opinion, which waste streams should be separated as risky to use, due to the possibility to contaminate the soil?

- A) Manure
- B) Plant residues
- C) Slurry
- D) Sewage sludge
- E) Compost
- F) Biochar
- G) Digestate

Those who participated in the survey believed that sewage sludge could pose the greatest threat to soil contamination. A significant 78.3% of respondents answered positively. 21.7% indicated a threat of digestate, and 6.5% of respondents believe that compost and biochar could also be sources of pollution.

Figure 8. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 8.

9. Is the quality of waste streams and their products important?

- A) Yes
- B) No

Almost all respondents answered positively to the question about whether they care about the quality of soil improvement products.

Figure 9. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 9.

10. Is it important for you that the quality of waste streams suitable for use in agriculture be regulated?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) I do not have opinion

For the majority of survey respondents, the quality of soil organic materials is important. However, there were a few who responded negatively or didn't have an opinion. This was the case for 28.5% of the farmer group and 25% of the entrepreneur group. It's likely that these are the same individuals who have never used soil improvement materials in their practice and don't intend to use them in the future.

Figure 10. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 10.

11. Is there enough information about the possibilities of using waste streams in agriculture?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) I don't care

In response to the question about whether there is sufficient information about soil improvement materials and their usage possibilities in the soil, only the entrepreneurs answered that there is enough information. The majority of surveyed scientists (62.5%) believe that there is insufficient information, a sentiment shared by 40% of farmers.

Figure 11. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 11.

12. Is the physical form of waste stream important to you? For example, liquid, solid, granular...

- A) Yes, I would use liquid
- B) Yes, I would use solid products
- C) Yes, I would use granular products
- D) No

The received answers indicate that for the majority of consumers, 41.3%, the physical form of organic materials being used is not important.

Figure 12. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 12.

13. What are the most effective ways to increase the use of waste streams in agriculture?

- A) Presentation of the results of scientific research on the benefits provided
- B) Financial support
- C) More information about the benefits provided in the media
- D) Practical conferences and presentations
- E) Other

In response to the question of how to increase the use of organic materials, the majority of respondents (71.7%) answered that the dissemination, demonstration, and presentation of scientific research would be effective. Following that, the second choice (58.7%) was the demonstration of practical results. As a third option (41.3%), respondents highlighted financial support as a means to encourage the use of organic soil improvement materials.

Figure 13. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 13.

14. In your opinion, how could the EU government encourage farmers to use more waste streams to improve soil quality and health?

- A) Prepare best practice guidelines for use
- B) Discounts for land tax
- C) Other financial support
- D) No additional activity is required
- E) Other

In response to the question about what actions the EU could take to increase the application of organic soil materials, two most popular choices can be highlighted: the preparation of using guidelines (69.6%) and financial support (52.2%).

Figure 14. Distribution of respondents' answers to question number 14.

8. Key remarks and conclusion

- Focus on strategies to cope with competition for these types of bio-circular waste streams

Future use of C-rich materials for a variety of applications including C storage in soil is expected to increase, potentially resulting in a shortage of these sources of exogenous organic matter. Using C-rich materials in a cascade is one strategy to avoid competition for these types of bio-circular waste streams. The use of C-rich materials as soil improver is relevant for Flanders, The Netherlands and other regions with intensive agriculture where manure is mainly used as source of nutrients, and where the addition of C to the soil with other materials/organic fertilizers is limited due to the legal limits for N and P input with fertilizers. As farmers prefer to use manure as source of nutrients for agricultural land, the addition of C-rich materials low in nutrients (e.g., materials with a high C/P ratio) is the only way they can add sources of exogeneous organic matter to the soil, but these

biomass types are also highly preferred for other applications, including their use in renewable horticultural substrates. WP3 results will contribute to the solution for this issue, by exploring the opportunities to use biomass in cascade in order to avoid competition for renewable biomass: case study on potential availability of alternative growing media constituents and the circular use of these materials (T3.2)

- The optimal application of bio-circular waste streams for soil health improvement

Processing techniques of waste streams may affect the impact on soil health indicators when these bio-circular waste streams are applied to the soil as organic fertilizer or soil improver.

BioCASH-WP3 results will contribute to the solution for this issue, by assessing the relation between soil health indicators for soil microbiology and soil organic content for the top soil of 5 long-term field trials with different renewable fertilizers and soil improvers, and effect of field history/spatial variability versus treatment effect on soil health indicator (link between soil management and the soil microbiome) (T3.3).

- Role of biochar for processing bio-circular waste streams and for soil application

Biochar is a promising technique for processing biomass and for long-term C storage, but biochar production in EU27 and the knowledge about the agricultural applications of biochar is still limited. WP3 results will contribute to tackle this knowledge gap, by exploring the opportunities to use biochar in cascade and the added value of biochar-based fertilizers: test combinations of biochar with ma.nure, compost, digestate, spent growing media, liquid fractions of waste treatment processes and routes for optimizing these combinations with biochar (T3.2).

Increased proportion of organic waste from waste material has increased the need to optimize the current levels of treatment techniques and the sustainable use of resulting waste products. If adequately harnessed, the interconnectivity between waste streams, farming systems, and sustainable agriculture is posed to enhance resource management, food security, and environmental conservation. Identifying waste streams and their processing technologies remains of primary concern in Europe, provided the byproducts would fit well and perform optimally in farming systems. Hence, optimizing treatment processes such as pyrolysis, anaerobic digestion, and composting remain relevant since the quality of the bio-circular waste is dependent on the treatment processes.

European farming systems range from small-scale organic farms to industrial operations, from conventional to regenerative. Increasingly, the principles of the circular economy through these bio-circular wastes (food waste, manure, and sewage sludge) are being embraced in European Agriculture. Waste from various agricultural and food processing activities is transformed into valuable products, such as biofertilizers, reducing waste and closing material loops. However, it must be noted that the utilization and performance of these bioproducts/processed waste streams are

dependent on factors such as diversity in climate, soil types, landscape, agricultural management and concept

9. References

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